

Metadata of the scripts regarding the manuscript “*A synthesis of land use impacts on stream biodiversity across metrics and scales*”

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Metadata of the scripts used in the manuscript “*A synthesis of land use impacts on stream biodiversity across metrics and scales*”. The public datasets used in this study are available at Zenodo: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3546213>.

1.1.alpha_MoB.R: Script to calculate the metrics of biodiversity (MoB) at alpha scale

1.2.alpha_MoB_models.R: Script to run the MoB models at alpha scale

1.3.alpha_MoB_plots.R: Script to plot the MoB results at alpha scale

2.1.gamma_MoB_extent.R: Script to calculate MoB at gamma scale using standardized extent data

2.2.gamma_MoB_extent_models.R: Script to run the MoB models at gamma scale using standardized extent data

2.3.gamma_MoB_extent_plots.R: Script to plot the MoB results at gamma scale using standardized extent data

3.1.a_beta_MoB_extent_paired.R: Script to calculate MoB at beta scale using a paired design and the standardized extent data

3.1.b_beta_MoB_extent_3_4str.R: Script to calculate metrics of biodiversity (MoB) at beta scale randomly sampling 3 or 4 streams using standardized extent data

3.2.beta_MoB_extent_models.R: Script to run the MoB models at beta scale using standardized extent data

3.3.beta_MoB_extent_plots.R: Script to plot the MoB results at beta scale using standardized extent data

3.4.beta_permdisp_extent_procedure.R: Script to calculate beta diversity within land use types using mean distance to centroid using standardized extent data

4.1.beta_among_extent.R: Script to calculate beta diversity among land use types using Sørensen and Bray-Curtis dissimilarity with standardized extent data

4.2.beta_among_extent_models.R: Script to run beta diversity among land use types models using Sørensen and Bray-Curtis dissimilarity with standardized extent data

4.3.beta_among_extent_plots.R: Script to plot the beta diversity among land use types results using Sørensen and Bray-Curtis dissimilarity with standardized extent data

5.Main_analyses_without_4studies.R: Script to repeat the main analysis excluding four streams with reference streams slightly more modified than in other studies (using all studies at alpha scale and using standardized extent data at gamma and beta scales)

6.Latitude.R: Script to calculate the relationship between land use type and latitude, and to repeat the main analysis including the interaction term between land use type and latitude in the models (using all studies at alpha scale and using standardized extent data at gamma and beta scales)